

**DEVELOPING ADVANCED MATHEMATICAL THINKING TEST
BASED ON PACE MODEL**

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Keywords:	ABSTRACT
Advanced Mathematical Thinking	The purpose of this research is to develop instrument of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test based on PACE model learning. This research developed essay tests that include indicators of Advanced Mathematical Thinking, namely: representation, abstraction, creative thinking, and mathematical proof on mathematical statistics course. This research was a developmental study. It used modification of Borg & Gall model. Stages of the model included: expert validation, limited trials (small scale), and respondent trials (large scale). Result of this research is: there are 11 items of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test which is feasible to be used to measure students' Advanced Mathematical Thinking who have received PACE model learning.
PACE Model	
Mathematical Statistics	

INTRODUCTION

Mathematical concepts in college are generally more complex than mathematical concepts in school because that concepts which is given in college are more abstract. Therefore, students of mathematics education program must have ability in constructing and finding mathematical concepts themselves, proving logically, and developing their mathematical abilities. This is very important for them in completing mathematical tasks in college, especially advanced mathematical courses (Sumarmo, 2011), such as Mathematical Statistics course.

To realize that expectation, students' mathematical thinking abilities should be developed and connected to mathematicians' thinking in order to create Advanced Mathematical Thinking abilities that focus more on formal definitions, logical deductions, and creative thinking (Tall, 2002). Advanced Mathematical Thinking ability include several components. There are representation, abstraction, connecting between representation and abstraction,

creative thinking, and mathematical proof (Sumarmo, 2011). However, the student' Advanced Mathematical Thinking, especially in Mathematics Statistics course is still relatively low and have difficulty in studying it.

Based on the results of Marron (1999) and Petocz & Smith (2007) studies that students of mathematics education program in Mathematical Statistics course have difficulties in mathematical proving process. In addition, based on the results of Suryana's study (2014a) that students have difficulty in studying mathematical statistics course, such as in presenting problems into other forms, generalizing, trying other ways of solving problems, reading mathematical proof, and constructing mathematical proof. In reading mathematical proofs, Suryana (2014b) in his study also revealed that students have difficulty in checking the truth and writing the concept which is used in each step of proof in Mathematical Statistics course.

To overcome these problems, the lecturers are expected to be able to manage the learning well. They give opportunities for students to construct the concept of Mathematical Statistics. One of

the models based on constructivism learning theory and it is predicted to be able to overcome the problem is PACE Model learning. The PACE model was developed by Lee (1999) for statistical learning which has 4 learning phases: Project, Activity, Cooperative Learning, and Exercise.

The project is an important component of PACE Model learning (Lee, 1999). It aims to apply concepts in everyday life. Project is done in groups. Students can choose their own project topics that are considered interesting. The procedure is given in the form of Project Sheet (PS). Meanwhile, activity in the PACE Model learning aims to introduce students to new information or concepts (Lee, 1999). This is done by assigning tasks in the form of Activity Sheet (AS). The role of it as a guide students in learning the material. Through AS, students are given the opportunity to discover their own concepts that will be studied.

For cooperative learning phase in the PACE Model learning, the student should discuss the solution of the problem in the Discussion Sheet (DS). DS is used to transform the knowledge that is gained at the activity phase. Through DS, students have opportunity to present the findings that is gained during discussion. Meanwhile, exercises in the PACE Model learning aims to reinforce concepts that have been constructed at activity and cooperative learning phases in the form of problem solving (Lee, 1999). This exercise is given to the students in the form of Exercise Sheet (ES). It is additional tasks to make the mastery of the material better.

To be able to learn more about the students' Advanced Mathematical Thinking who have received PACE model learning on Mathematical Statistics Course, it is necessary to develop instrument of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test based on PACE Model. The purpose of this research is to develop instrument of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test based on PACE Model.

Through this research, it is expected to be a reference for the practitioners of mathematics education in developing instrumen of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test based on PACE Model.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research was a developmental study. Instrumen that was depeolved in this research was Advanced Mathematical Thinking test based on PACE Model learning. This research was conducted in Mathematics Education Program, Indraprasta PGRI University, Jakarta. This research used modification of Borg & Gall model (1983). The stages of that model were as follows:

- 1) Reviewing the literature and doing observation
- 2) Composing instrument of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test
- 3) Doing expert validation on instrument of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test that have been composed. This validation includes: face validity and content validity. That validators were 5 people who experts in the field, namely: a Doctor of Statistics, 2 Master of Mathematics who were studying in Doctoral program, and 2 Master of Mathematics Education who were studying in Doctoral program.
- 4) Doing revisions based on suggestions from experts.
- 5) Doing limited trials (small scale) on instrument of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test to students of Mathematics Education Program, Indraprasta PGRI university, Jakarta who have obtained Mathematical Statistics material to know: (a) readability and comprehension of questions of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test by the students; and (b) sufficiency of test time that was written in Mathematical Advanced Thinking test.
- 6) Doing revisions based on suggestions from limited trials (small scale).

7) Doing respondent trials (large scale) on instrument of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test to students of Mathematics Program, Indraprasta PGRI university who have obtained Mathematical Statistics material to know: (a) validity, (b) reliability, (c) discriminatory power, and (d) level of difficulty to get final instrument of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Advanced Mathematical Thinking test are used to measure the students' Advanced Mathematical Thinking ability, including: representation, abstraction, creative thinking, and mathematical proof on mathematical statistics course. Advanced Mathematical Thinking test was developed by the researcher in form of essay tests so that the flow of students' thinking in solving the problem is more clearly illustrated. The following was result of development research that used modification of Borg & Gall model.

Result of instrument of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test that has been composed

After Reviewing the literature and doing observation about Advanced Mathematical Thinking, then composing instrument of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test on mathematical statistics course. Indicators of Advanced Mathematical Thinking (AMT) test that has been developed has given in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1. Indicators of AMT Part-A

No.	Component of AMT	Aspect that is measured	Indicator	Number of Item
1	Representation	Presenting problems in other forms	Create an image of domain area of joint density function based on transformation of two random variables and determine function of marginal density based on that image that is created	4
2	Abstraction	Synthesize	Determine probability of an event from an order statistic of two random variables	6
			Determine probability of an event from an order statistic of three random variables	7
		Generalize	Compose general form of probability of an event from an order statistic of n random variables	8
3	Creative Thinking	Fluency	Write two functions of x and y that qualify as joint density function	1
		Flexibility	Determine expected value of two continuous random variables by choosing one way	2
		Originality	Determine transformation form that is used in a case by unusual way	5
		Elaboration	Express information becomes a mathematical problem that can be solved and explain its' solution	3

Table 2. Indicators of AMT Part-B

No.	Component of AMT	Aspect that is measured	Indicator	Number of Item
4	Mathematical proof	Reading of proof	Examine truth of each step of proof and write the concepts that is used in relation to bivariate normal distribution	3
			Examine truth of each step of proof and write the concepts that is used in relation to density function of $X + Y$	4
		Construct of proof	Compose of proof in related to stochastic independence	1
			Compose of proof in related to bivariate normal distribution	2

Result of Expert Validation

Validation by experts includes: face validity and content validity. The indicators are as follows:

- 1) The indicators of face validity are: (a) using good language, (b) no ambiguity, (c) using common

language, and (d) easy to be understood.

- The indicators of content validity are suitability between number of item of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test and component, aspect that is measured, and indicator of Advanced Mathematical Thinking.

Experts assess instrument of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test by writing 'number 1' if the statement is valid, and 'number 0' if it is invalid. The results of face validity and content validity are processed and analyzed using Q-Cochran test that is helped by Software of SPSS 21.0. Q-Cochran test aims to determine whether the experts do consideration to items of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test uniformly or not. The hypothesis is as follows:

- H_0 : Experts do consideration uniformly
 H_1 : Experts do consideration not uniformly

Criteria of hypothesis testing that is used in this research is 'if value of asymp.Sig > 0.05, then H_0 accepted', and 'otherwise, then H_0 is rejected'. Results of expert validation are given in the following table.

Table 3. Results of Experts' Consideration on Face Validity of Advanced Mathematical Thinking Test

	Number of item	Experts				
		1	2	3	4	5
Part-A	1	1	1	0	1	1
	2	1	1	1	1	1
	3	1	1	1	1	1
	4	1	1	1	1	1
	5	1	1	1	1	1
	6	1	1	1	1	1
	7	1	1	1	1	1
	8	1	1	1	1	1
Part-B	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2	1	1	1	1	1
	3	1	1	1	1	1
	4	1	1	1	1	1

Note: 1 = Valid, 0 = Invalid

Table 4. Results of Experts' Consideration on Content Validity of Advanced Mathematical Thinking Test

	Number of item	Experts				
		1	2	3	4	5
Part-A	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2	1	1	1	1	1
	3	1	1	1	1	1
	4	1	1	1	1	1
	5	1	1	1	1	1
	6	1	1	1	1	1
	7	1	1	1	1	1
	8	1	1	1	1	1
Part-B	1	1	1	1	1	1
	2	1	1	1	1	1
	3	1	1	1	1	1
	4	1	1	1	1	1

Note: 1 = Valid, 0 = Invalid

Furthermore, the results of face validity were processed and analyzed using Q-Cochran test. The results are as follows:

Table 5. Results of Face Validity of Advanced Mathematical Thinking Test

Q-Cochran	n	df	Asymp. Sig.
4,000 ^a	12	4	0,406

Based on Table 5, it is seen that the value of asymp.Sig > 0.05. Thus, it can be concluded that the experts have consideration uniformly related to face validity of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test (valid). Meanwhile, the results of content validity were not processed and analyzed using Q-Cochran test because all item of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test have number 1 (see Table 4). In other words, the experts have consideration uniformly related to content validity of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test (valid).

Suggestion of experts on item of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test were as follows:

- For question No. 1 of Part A, the sentence "Write two functions of x and y that qualify as joint probability function" was changed to "Write two random variable functions of x and y

- that qualify as a joint probability function".
- 2) For the question No. 2 of Part A, the phrase "An electronic have main components A and B" was changed to "An electronic device have main components A and B", and the phrase "How many ways to determine expectation value of total of usage duration on both components of electronic?" was changed to "How many ways to determine expectation value of total of usage duration on both components of electronic device?".
 - 3) Required revisions related to calculation in answer keys of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test.

Result of limited trials (small scale) on instrument of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test

After the questions of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test were repaired in accordance with experts' suggestions, then that instrument was done limited trials (small scale) to 5 students who have passed the Mathematical Statistics Course.

Based on the results of limited trial (small scale), it can be concluded that the question of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test can be well understood by students and the time that is written on Mathematical Thinking test is considered enough.

Result of respondent trials (large scale) on instrument of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test

After the questions of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test were repaired in accordance with result of limited trial (small scale), then that instrument was done respondent trials (large scale) to 52 students who have passed the Mathematical Statistics Course.

The question of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test consists two parts, namely part A and part B. The question of part A is related to the three components of Advanced Mathematical

Thinking, namely: representation, abstraction, and mathematical creative thinking with time of work is 120 minutes; While the test part B related to 1 component of Advanced Mathematical Thinking, that is mathematical proof with time of work is 90 minutes.

The purpose of giving Advanced Mathematical Thinking test to the students into 2 parts to be done in different time is to avoid the students from saturation and stress factors because the number of questions to be done is too much. This trial is used to determine: (1) validity, (2) reliability, (3) discriminatory power, and (4) level of difficulty to get final instrument of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test.

1) Validity

Determining the validity of each item of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test is done by calculating correlation between score of each item of the test with total score. This correlation calculation is done by using Product Moment correlation formula from Pearson (Suherman, 2003).

Processing and data analysis of trial results in determining the validity of test items is helped by Software of SPSS 21.0. The correlation values at SPSS output (r-count) are taken from the "Corrected Item-Total Correlated" column (Ghozali, 2006).

To know the test item is valid or not, then the value of r-count is compared with the value of the Product Moment table (r-table with $dk = n-2$ and $\alpha = 0,05$). If the value of r-count > r-table, then the test item is valid, and otherwise, then the test item is invalid (Ghozali, 2006). The results of validity on item of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test are given in Table 6.

Table 6. Results of Validity on Item of Advanced Mathematical Thinking Test

Part	Number of item	Corrected Item-Total Correlation
A	1	0,41
	2	0,50
	3	0,35
	4	0,63
	5	0,29
	6	0,63
	7	0,60
	8	0,33
B	1	0,58
	2	0,29
	3	0,36
	4	-0,10

Based on Table 6, it can be seen that there are 11 items of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test that have the value of r -count $>$ r -table (0,279), so that it can be said that 11 items are valid.

2) Reliability

Reliability of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test using a single test. The test is given to a group of students in a single meeting in order to be obtained data. Furthermore, that data was calculated reliability coefficient. In this research, the determination of reliability coefficient using Cronbach Alpha formula (Suherman, 2003) because Advanced Mathematical Thinking test that is composed is essay test.

Processing and data analysis of trial results in determining the reliability of test items is helped by Software of SPSS 21.0. Interpretation of reliability coefficients according to Guilford (Suherman, 2003) are as follows:

Table 7. Interpretation of Reliability Coefficients

Reliability Coefficients (r_{11})	Interpretation
$0,90 \leq r_{11} \leq 1,00$	The reliability is very high
$0,70 \leq r_{11} < 0,90$	The reliability is high
$0,40 \leq r_{11} < 0,70$	The reliability is medium
$0,20 \leq r_{11} < 0,40$	The reliability is low
$r_{11} < 0,20$	The reliability is very low

The result of reliability on Advanced Mathematical Thinking test are given in the following table:

Table 8. Result of Reliability on Advanced Mathematical Thinking Test

Cronbach Alpha	n
0,78	12

Based on Table 8, it can be seen that $r_{11} = 0,78$ so it can be said that Advanced Mathematical Thinking test has a high reliability.

3) Discriminatory Power

Discriminatory power of test item aims to distinguish between testee who have a high skill and testee who have a low skill. If testee who have a high skill can do test well and testee who have a low skill can not do test well, it is said that the test items have good discriminatory power (Arikunto, 2012).

Steps to determine discriminatory power of each test item are as follows:

- a) Sort scores of testee' test from highest to lowest.
- b) Divide scores of testee' test into two groups: 27% of testee who have high scores as top group and 27% of testee who have low scores as bottom group (Suherman, 2003).
- c) Calculating discriminatory power of each test item with the following formula (Suherman, 2003):

$$DP = \frac{JB_A - JB_B}{JS_A}$$

Note:

- DP = Discriminatory power
- JB_A = Total scores of testee' test on top group that is processed

JB_B = Total scores of testee' test on bottom group that is processed

JS_A = Total of ideal scores for one of groups (top) on the test items that is processed

Calculating discriminatory power of each test item is helped by Software of *Microsoft Excel 2007*. Interpretation of discriminatory power of each test item is given in the following table (Suherman, 2003):

Table 9. Interpretation of Discriminatory Power

Discriminatory Power (DP)	Interpretation
$DP \leq 0,00$	Very Bad
$0,00 < DP \leq 0,20$	Bad
$0,20 < DP \leq 0,40$	Enough
$0,40 < DP \leq 0,70$	Good
$0,70 < DP \leq 1,00$	Very Good

The results of discriminatory power on item of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test and its' interpretation are given in the following table:

Table 10. Results of Discriminatory Power on Item of Advanced Mathematical Thinking Test

	Number of item	Discriminatory Power	Interpretation
Part-A	1	0,39	Enough
	2	0,48	Good
	3	0,25	Enough
	4	0,45	Good
	5	0,21	Enough
	6	0,68	Good
	7	0,73	Very Good
	8	0,32	Enough
Part-B	1	0,46	Good
	2	0,21	Enough
	3	0,39	Enough
	4	0,00	Very Bad

4) Level of Difficulty

Level of difficulty aims to find out whether the question of test is easy, medium, or difficult. The test item is said to be good if the item is not too easy and not too difficult (Arikunto, 2012).

Steps to determine level of difficulty of each test item are as follows:

- Sort scores of testee' test from highest to lowest.
- Divide scores of testee' test into two groups: 27% of testee who have high scores as top group and 27% of testee who have low scores as bottom group (Suherman, 2003).
- Calculating level of difficulty of each test item with the following formula (Suherman, 2003):

$$IK = \frac{JB_A + JB_B}{2JS_A}$$

Note:

IK = Level of difficulty

JB_A = Total scores of testee' test on top group that is processed

JB_B = Total scores of testee' test on bottom group that is processed

JS_A = Total of ideal scores for one of groups (top) on the test items that is processed

Calculating level of difficulty of each test item is helped by Software of *Microsoft Excel 2007*. Interpretation of level of difficulty of each test item is given in the following table (Suherman, 2003):

Table 11. Interpretation of Level of Difficulty

Level of Difficulty (IK)	Interpretation
$IK = 0,00$	The question is too difficult
$0,00 < IK \leq 0,30$	The question is difficult
$0,30 < IK \leq 0,70$	The question is medium
$0,70 < DP \leq 1,00$	The question is easy
$IK = 1,00$	The question is too easy

The results of level of difficulty on item of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test and its' interpretation are given in the following table:

Table 12. Results of Level of Difficulty on Item of Advanced Mathematical Thinking Test

	Number of item	Level of Difficulty	Interpretation
Part-A	1	0,43	medium
	2	0,38	medium
	3	0,32	medium
	4	0,40	medium
	5	0,20	difficult
	6	0,50	medium
	7	0,51	medium
	8	0,30	difficult
Part-B	1	0,52	medium
	2	0,27	difficult
	3	0,32	medium
	4	0,23	difficult

Recapitulation of result of respondent trials (large scale) on instrument of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test is given in Table 13. Based on Table 13, it can be said that there are 11 items of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test which is feasible to be used to measure students' Advanced Mathematical Thinking who have received PACE model learning., namely:

- a) 8 items from test of Part A. That are: No. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8.
- b) 3 items from test of Part B. That are: No. 1, 2, and 3.

Table 13. Recapitulation of Result of Respondent Trials on Instrument of Advanced Mathematical Thinking Test

Number of Item	Validity	Reliability	Discriminatory Power	Level of Difficulty	Interpretation
Part-A	1	0,41 Valid	0,39 Enough	0,43 Medium	Used
	2	0,50 Valid	0,48 Good	0,38 Medium	Used
	3	0,35 Valid	0,25 Enough	0,32 Medium	Used
	4	0,63 Valid	0,45 Good	0,40 Medium	Used
	5	0,29 Valid	0,21 Enough	0,20 Difficult	Used
	6	0,63 Valid	0,68 Good	0,50 Medium	Used
	7	0,60 Valid	0,73 Very Good	0,51 Medium	Used
	8	0,33 Valid	0,32 Enough	0,30 Difficult	Used
Part-B	1	0,58 Valid	0,46 Good	0,52 Medium	Used
	2	0,29 Valid	0,21 Enough	0,27 Difficult	Used
	3	0,36 Valid	0,39 Enough	0,32 Medium	Used
	4	-0,10 Invalid	0,00 Very Bad	0,23 Difficult	Not Used

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Conclusion

There are 11 items of Advanced Mathematical Thinking test which is feasible to be used to measure students' Advanced Mathematical Thinking who have received PACE model learning.

Suggestion

The instruments that is developed can be used to measure the achievement and enhancement of students' Advanced Mathematical Thinking who have received PACE model learning.

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